

Педагог и издатель Ф. Ф. Павленков в вятской ссылке

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Выдающийся российский просветитель, педагог, методист и издатель Флорентий Федорович Павленков (1839-1900) провел несколько лет в вятской ссылке (1869-1877). Пребывание Павленкова в ссылке в губернском городе Вятке, а также в уездном городе Яранске Вятской губернии, сопровождалось его большой активностью в деле создания методической литературы для начальной школы и издания полезной просветительской литературы. *Цель статьи* – дать оценку просветительской и издательской деятельности Павленкова, и показать ее позитивное влияние на развитие просвещения в российской провинции, в частности, в Вятской губернии.

Материалы и методы. В работе автор использовал сравнительно-сопоставительный метод и метод ретроспективного анализа, региональный и аксиологический методологические подходы. Применение указанных методов и подходов позволило выявить ценностное содержание в методической, издательской и просветительской работе Ф. Ф. Павленкова.

Результаты. Методическая, издательская и просветительская деятельность Ф. Ф. Павленкова в период его пребывания в ссылке в городах Вятка и Яранск имела важное значение для культурно-образовательного развития местного населения. В результате проводившейся им работы было издано значительное количество ценных книг, прежде всего, «Вятская незабудка», «Наглядная азбука», а также других изданий, сыгравших свою позитивную роль в просвещении вятчан.

Обсуждение. Объективный анализ деятельности Павленкова дает основание считать его видной фигурой российского просвещения второй половины XIX в. Отечественные биографы Павленкова (А. В. Блюм, Ю. А. Горбунов, Н. П. Изергина, Н. М. Рассудовская и др.) исключительно высоко оценивали его усилия по просвещению русского народа. Основанная им серия биографических книг «Жизнь замечательных людей» получила свое продолжение в XX-XXI вв. В наши дни возникло целое движение сельских «Павленковских библиотек», ставящих в основу своей деятельности просвещение народа, прежде всего, сельских жителей.

Заключение. Ф. Ф. Павленков – один из крупнейших российских просветителей, видный педагог-методист, издатель литературы для народа. Его личность стоит в одном ряду с наиболее видными деятелями просвещения России XIX в.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

Вятская губерния, Павленков, выдающийся издатель, просветитель и педагог-методист, Писарев, ссылка, Вятка, Яранск, «Вятская Незабудка», Блинов, «Наглядная азбука», Павленковские библиотеки

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Teacher and publisher F. F. Pavlenkov in Vyatka exile

V. B. POMELOV

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The outstanding Russian educator, teacher, methodologist and publisher Florenty Fedorovich Pavlenkov (1839-1900) spent several years in Vyatka exile (1869-1877). Pavlenkov's stay in exile in the provincial city of Vyatka, as well as in the county town of Yaransk in the Vyatka province, was accompanied by his great activity in creating methodological literature for elementary schools and publishing useful educational literature. *The purpose of the article* is to evaluate Pavlenkov's educational and publishing activities, and to show its positive impact on the development of education in the Russian province, in particular, in the Vyatka province.

Materials and methods. The author used the comparative method and the method of retrospective analysis, regional and axiological methodological approaches. The application of these methods and approaches allowed us to identify the value content in the methodological, publishing and educational work of F. F. Pavlenkov.

Results. F. F. Pavlenkov's methodical, publishing and educational activities during his stay in exile in the cities of Vyatka and Yaransk were important for the cultural and educational development of the local population. As a result of his work, a significant number of valuable books were published, first of all, "Vyatka Forget-me-not", "Visual Alphabet", as well as other publications that played a positive role in educating the people of Vyatka.

Discussion. An objective analysis of Pavlenkov's activity gives reason to consider him a prominent figure of the Russian enlightenment of the second half of the XIX century. Russian biographers of Pavlenkov (A.V. Blum, Yu. A. Gorbunov, N. P. Izergina, N. M. Rassudovskaya, etc.) highly appreciated his efforts to educate Russian people. The series of biographical books founded by him "The Life of remarkable people" was continued in the XX-XXI centuries. Nowadays, a whole movement of rural "Pavlenkov libraries" has emerged, which base their activities on the education of the people, primarily rural residents.

Conclusion. F. F. Pavlenkov is one of the largest Russian educators, a prominent methodologist, publisher of literature for the people. His personality is on a par with the most prominent figures of the enlightenment of Russia of the XIX century.

KEYWORDS

Vyatka province, Pavlenkov, an outstanding publisher, educator and methodologist, Pisarev, exile, Vyatka, Yaransk, "Vyatka Forget-me-not", Blinov, "Visual Alphabet", Pavlenkov libraries

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INTRODUCTION

In historical and pedagogical science, considerable attention is paid to the activities of prominent teachers who have shown themselves in one or another section of the science of education, for example, in the field of didactics [1]. Scientists are constantly searching for better teaching methods [2]. An important place in these studies is given to the use of the project method [3]. It's even sometimes interpreted as an alternative to traditional methods [4]. A particularly important place is given to it in natural sciences [5]. It also finds application in study of foreign languages, acting as a means of activating students' thinking [6]. Traditional methods (problematic, use of video, etc.) are also constantly in the focus of attention of scientists and practitioners [7]. As before, use of books and textbooks is given great importance in research; literature is called an instrument of consolation, a means of education [8]. A significant place in research is occupied by characteristics of educational efforts that have received universal recognition [9]. Quite often, researchers analyze the activities of teachers who worked in different areas of pedagogical and educational activities [10]. Especially often such pedagogical figures manifested themselves in province [11]. There were many female teachers among them [12]. Attempts at enlightenment in remote regions of Russia were especially important [13]. One of such important figures of enlightenment, who made a convincing and significant contribution to native education, was the outstanding Russian publisher Florenty Fedorovich Pavlenkov. Of particular importance was his activity in the development of education and the promotion of humanistic ideas and views among the population of the Vyatka province, since here he was in political exile in 1869-1877.

At the beginning of the 20th century, Vyatka province saw an active development of educational activities, in which national libraries played an important role. The Vyatka Zemstvo actively supported their opening, believing that without libraries it's impossible to ensure the widespread dissemination of literacy and education, especially in rural areas. The creation of the Pavlenkov libraries significantly contributed to the further expansion of the library network in the province. For a long time, no targeted work has been carried out to identify and study the condition of the Pavlenkov libraries in the Kirov region.

However, in recent years, 84 libraries have been registered and certified, and materials about their history have been collected in some counties. The result of the work done was the creation of the Kirov Branch of the UNESCO Pavlenkov Library Association. Its founding conference was attended by 30 rural librarians from different districts of the Kirov region. Based on the above, we see that the legacy of Pavlenkov, in the form of books published by him and libraries opened with his money, continues to serve the benefit of people, and his name has entered the history of Russian culture as an example of selfless service for the enlightenment of the people. In this regard, we formulated the purpose of the study, which is to evaluate Pavlenkov's educational and publishing activities, and demonstrate its positive impact on the development of education in the Russian province, in particular, in the Vyatka province.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The leading research methods used in the preparation of this article are the analysis of scientific literature, memoir and autobiographical documents, journalistic publications and review; biographical and historical methods, as well as regional and axiological approaches. The latter opens up a wide opportunity to identify the most valuable content in the subject of research. The author used materials published in leading scientific domestic and foreign journals, including "History of Education & Children's Literature", "Pedagogy", "European Journal of Contemporary Education", "IEEE Latin America Transactions", "International Journal for Lesson and Learning Studies", "Advances in Higher Education", "Integration of education", "The European Journal of Social Education", "Espacio, Tiempo y Educación", as well as materials of collections of scientific conferences, works of Russian and foreign researchers in the sphere of the history of pedagogy and education, in particular, M. J. Madrid, C. López-Esteban, C. León-Mantero, L. Kaminskienė, V. Žydžiūnaitė, V. Jurgilė, T. Ponomarenko, G. Fuertes, A. V. Blum, Yu. A. Gorbunov, L. M. Dobrovolsky, N. P. Izergina, E. D. Petryaev, etc.

RESULTS

Biographical facts

F. F. Pavlenkov was born on October 8 (20), 1839 in a poor landowner family in Kirsanovsky district of Tambov province. At the age of seven, he lost his parents and was taken in by his mother's sister. She decided to send him to the Tsarskoye Selo Alexander Cadet Corps for young orphans from the nobility. In 1859, Florenty graduated from the 1st Cadet Corps on Vasilevsky Island in St. Petersburg with the rank of lieutenant, and was assigned to a rifle battalion with a secondment to the Mikhailovsky Artillery Academy, where he completed the course of study in 1861. He served in the horse artillery in the Kiev and Bryansk arsenals, but he showed a penchant for literary pursuits, which attracted the attention of chief of military educational institutions Ya. I. Rostovtsev. One of poems of cadet Pavlenkov pleased Rostovtsev so much that he even awarded him a gold watch and organized a performance in front of the royal family. The details of this event remained unknown, because later Pavlenkov didn't like to remember about it. Presumably, poems were filled with monarchic feelings.

During the course at the Academy, Pavlenkov studied physics, chemistry and artillery engineering; he was especially interested in studying the history of ancient rifled guns. The result of this interest was his first printed work, marked September 15, 1860, and it appeared in the "Artillery Journal" under the title "About old rifled guns stored in the St. Petersburg Arsenal." Military service wasn't too burdensome, so Pavlenkov became interested in translation work. Moreover, he began to translate from French a complex scientific work, – the "Course of Physics" by A. Gano. He had the idea to undertake the publication of the book at his own expense, and ordered 4,000 copies and soon, in the summer of 1867, the circulation was sold out.

At the end of 1865 Pavlenkov got acquainted with the family of D. I. Pisarev, his mother Varvara Dmitrievna and his older sister Vera, who became his common-law wife. Pisarev himself had been in prison since 1862. Pavlenkov enthusiastically read his articles in the "Russian Word". Publication of Gano's "Physics" met his expectations, – it was possible to sell the entire circulation! Pavlenkov decided to try to publish Pisarev's works, about which he wrote to him. The 25-year-old critic and publicist accepted Pavlenkov's offer with delight. However, soon disagreements arose between them. Pavlenkov recognized the need for Pisarev, for censorship reasons, to make some changes to the text of one or two articles, but he refused to "soften" the text. As a result, as soon as the 2nd volume was printed (June 2, 1866), the arrest of the entire circulation immediately followed.

The writings of Pisarev were also read by Vyatka youth, in particular, a high school student, the son of a Polish exile, the future founder of cosmonautics K. E. Tsiolkovsky. He wrote in his memoirs: "Pisarev made me tremble with joy and happiness. At that time I saw in him the second "I"... This is one of my most respected teachers" [14, p. 131].

The sphere of book publishing fascinated Pavlenkov more and more. He retired from military service in 1866 with the rank of lieutenant. Florenty devoted himself entirely to the publication and distribution of books; he began publishing a series of books on natural science and natural philosophy.

On July 4, 1868, while swimming in the sea in Dubelnya, near Riga, Pisarev drowned. Pavlenkov had a sad need to take care of the funeral. A large crowd of Pisarev's admirers gathered at the Volkov Cemetery. Despite the ban, Pavlenkov made a farewell speech, which later became a formal reason for his persecution by authorities. At the funeral, a proposal was made to perpetuate the memory of Pisarev by establishing a scholarship in his name and installing a monument. The same idea was expressed in many newspapers, and Pavlenkov's bookstore began to receive numerous requests and suggestions about this from different parts of Russia. Pavlenkov had to answer all requests personally. This has overwhelmed the patience of authorities. On September 3, 1868, he was arrested and after a search of his apartment and bookstore, which didn't reveal anything illegal, he was placed first in the Spasskaya unit, and then in the Peter and Paul Fortress. Pavlenkov had no doubt about intentions of police to expel him from the capital in order to deprive him of an opportunity to continue his book publishing activities, the ideological orientation of which the government didn't like. On June 11, 1869, he was exiled to Vyatka.

Pavlenkov's activities in the Vyatka province

Immediately upon arrival in Vyatka, in July of the same year, Pavlenkov was officially announced, "with the withdrawal of his subscription," that he was forbidden to engage in publishing activities. But he couldn't leave the business that had become the main thing in his life. But it was necessary to live on something. In the Vyatka Provincial Gazette (1869, no. 20), an announcement appeared: "A person who knows French well wants to give lessons in his house. Apartment in the house of Ivan Petrovich Shuravin" [14, p. 131]. This "person" was Pavlenkov: he couldn't openly give his last name; he was forbidden to engage in teaching.

During the Vyatka period of Pavlenkov's life, the following directions of his enlightenment activities are distinguished: the unification of progressive, democratically minded local creative forces in order to create journalistic literature, primarily the "Vyatka Forget-me-Not", the publication of scientific and methodological textbooks and the compilation of the "Visual Alphabet".

In Vyatka, Pavlenkov stood at the head of a kind of circle, – "artel", as he himself put it, – which included the entire color of the then Vyatka progressive-minded intelligentsia. They were writer Maria Egorovna Selenkina (nee. Myshkina) (1844-1894), artist Viktor Mikhailovich Vasnetsov (1848-1926), exiled revolutionary democrat, ethnographer Vasily Fedorovich Troshchansky (1843-1898), owner of the printing house and the first private Vyatka library Alexander Alexandrovich Krasovsky (1828-1883), teachers Nikolai Nikolaevich Blinov (1839-1917) and Matvey Leontievich Peskovsky (1843-1903), chairman of the provincial zemstvo board Matvey Matveyevich Sintsov (1835-1910), official and publicist, participant in the revolutionary movement of the 1860s, doctor Veniamin Osipovich Portugalov, zemstvo doctor Savvaty Ivanovich Sychugov (1841-1902), as well as officials I. N. Romanov and A. A. Syrnev, surgeon A. N. Rudnev, etc.

Among Pavlenkov's Vyatka friends was the exiled teacher Vasily Ivanovich Obreimov (1843-1910), a passionate admirer of Pisarev's views and his pedagogical ideas. Later he became a famous methodist-mathematician; his book "Mathematical Sophisms" was admired by V. I. Lenin [15, p. 25]. Another representative of Pavlenkov's Vyatka entourage was the son of the Vyatka archpriest Vladimir Ignatievich Farmakovskiy (1842-1922), later a well-known pedagogical figure. In Vyatka, in Krasovsky's printing house, Pavlenkov published in several editions six Farmakovskiy books, which served as manuals for judges, foremen and jurors.

In 1874, Kazan publicist and local historian N. Ya. Agafonov visited Vyatka. Later, in a letter to the Nizhny Novgorod historian and statistician Alexander Serafimovich Gatsissky (1838-1893), he indicated that he advised the Pavlenkov circle to publish, due to the presence of a significant number of literary forces in Vyatka, a satirical newspaper [15, pp. 8-9]. This idea was soon realized by the release of three collections of articles with the general title "Vyatka Forget-me-not", which contained materials of sharply incriminating content. The minister of internal affairs reported to the cabinet of ministers: "Vyatka Forget-me-Not" is a collection of exclusively accusatory and libellous stories about government and public institutions of the Vyatka province, about local officials, starting with parish clerks and prison guards and reaching the governor and bishop. But this impression goes further, since revolutionary ideas are carried out on the pages of this book" [16, p. 129].

The first volume was published in St. Petersburg, in 1877. It became the first publication in Russia whose authors openly criticized the autocracy. "Vyatka forget-me-not" was a significant volume of collections of journalistic satirical articles, the content of which was directed against central and local authorities. Already in the titles of many articles ("Biting Sheep", "Bribery Artel", "Real shit", etc.), and even more so in their content, authors of the publication actively used such features of the literary style of M. E. Saltykov-Shchedrin as image deformation, hyperbole, grotesque, irony, "puppetry", zoological assimilation, etc.

Several articles were devoted to education issues. In them, in particular, it was noted that the county zemstvos don't care enough about the development of education. Even in the Malmyzh district, where "the most significant zemstvo in the whole Vyatka province", half of its volosts remained without schools. The article "The Question of mobile schools" critically assessed activities of the Yaransk zemstvo, whose annual meeting was a "real battlefield": "A new three-year anniversary has come, and with it new chances to participate in the division of the zemstvo pie" [17, pp. 198-199].

DISCUSSION

The most notable event in Pavlenkov's publications was the capital work of the director of the Roman Observatory and priest Angelo Secchi, in which he tried to "reconcile" conclusions of science with a recognition of the existence of God. The Italian abbot believed that "science perfectly connects with the position of the existence of God." In fact, this work to some extent anticipated the emergence of such an influential philosophical trend as neotomism. While working on the translation of the book, Pavlenkov sought to preserve all really valuable scientific provisions, omitting author's religious and mystical reasoning, because, being a supporter of teaching of Ch. Darwin, he couldn't allow to attack this doctrine. Secchi's book, published in Vyatka, had as appendices the works of Barker and Tyndall mentioned above, previously published in separate pamphlets.

Professor of the Moscow theological academy E. E. Golubinsky responded to this publication with an article "Secchi's book "The unity of physical forces" and the trends of its Vyatka edition in Russian", published in the magazine "Orthodox Review" (1875). The "review", which had the character of a political denunciation, noted cases of "inaccurate translation", omissions in the original text, atheistic tendencies of the translator and publisher, who sought to avoid using words such as "god", "creator of the world", "founder", "deity", etc. [18, p. 41]. Golubinsky sent prints of the article to Vyatka bishop, rector of the theological academy, police chief and vice-governor Domelunksen. Vyatka Bishop Apollon asked the General Directorate for Press Affairs to withdraw the book of Secchi translated by Pavlenkov from sale. It's amazing, but the fact is that the General Directorate considered that there were no statements against religion in the book, – it was simply not mentioned, – and therefore the request was left without satisfaction. Nevertheless, local authorities, heeding the bishop's suggestion, sent Pavlenkov to Yaransk as punishment [16, p. 18]. Later, in February 1880, V. G. Korolenko asked Pavlenkov, meeting him in the Vyshny Volochok prison, why he had deleted theological passages from Secchi's book. Pavlenkov remarked indignantly: "Of course! I wouldn't spread Jesuit sophistry!" [19, p. 108].

Nevertheless, the release of this book was the reason for Pavlenkov's "hiding" in an even more distant exile, – in the Vyatka county town of Yaransk. Pavlenkov was transferred there on January 14, 1876, and he lived there until November of the same year. In Yaransk, local public figures became his friends: secretary of the zemstvo board V. M. Gusev, candidate of forestry studies, forester E. E. Wallenburger and zemstvo architect I. A. Shmakov. Together they discussed the possibility of opening the Vyatka zemsky vestnik, the establishment of mobile schools and other topical issues. Pavlenkov continued preparing for publication of the "Practical course of the Italian language by the Ollendorff method" [20, p. 40].

The beginning of one of his most significant works belongs to the period of Yaransk exile, – preparation for publication of the Illustrated Word Interpreter, the first 10 printed sheets of which were completed in Yaransk. The publication, as a result, was released in St. Petersburg in 1899 under the title "Pavlenkov Encyclopedic Dictionary". After his death, his successors published the dictionary in five editions in 1905-1913. The total circulation of it exceeded 100000 copies, which far exceeded the circulation of any encyclopedic publication at that time. In addition, it was in Yaransk that he conceived the publication of the Vyatka Forget-me-Not. The Vyatka governor expressed dissatisfaction with Pavlenkov's negative influence on members of the Yaransky county zemstvo, and preferred to return him to Vyatka, under his personal supervision. The inherent desire of Pavlenkov to enlighten people is clearly manifested in his correspondence with the most prominent representatives of Russian public thought and pedagogical science and practice (Pisarev, Korf, Bunakov, Paulson, etc.), in the publication of numerous textbooks, in the dissemination of the progressive idea of mobile schools.

Pavlenkov wasn't only a qualified translator, a progressive publisher and a fearless publicist, but also a well-known methodist. Moreover, his methodical talent was especially clearly manifested during the period of Vyatka exile. On basis of the original version of the visual-sound method of literacy teaching developed by him, he compiled a "Visual Alphabet", published in 1873 in Vyatka and St. Petersburg. The authorship of this manual was at first really attributed to N. N. Blinov, since Pavlenkov couldn't, for censorship reasons, publish it under his own name. Therefore, he asked Blinov to put his, Blinov's, surname on a cover, since works of Nikolai Nikolaevich himself were censored without complications at that time, and he enjoyed the trust of official authorities.

"Visual Alphabet" was a textbook equipped with a large number of drawings that facilitated the assimilation of letters without help of a teacher. The purpose of compiling his manual Pavlenkov saw in making the process of learning to read and write more accessible and enjoyable for students. In addition to the manual, he also published a methodological manual "Explanation to Visual Alphabet", in which he explained the essence of his method. His method is based on the following consideration, Pavlenkov pointed out, according to which, knowing the sum of two numbers and one of the terms, it's not difficult to find the other term. "Objects were selected in such a way that the difference remaining at the end of the signature under the drawing was the desired sound, as if standing out by itself" [21, p. 4]. All the more important for the characterization of Pavlenkov's manuals were positive reviews of prominent teachers. Thus, D. D. Semenov, pointing out particular shortcomings of "Visual Alphabet", saw the great merit of the author in the development of principle of clarity in teaching Russian literacy [22, p. 182].

The first "skirmishers" who marched against the "Visual Alphabet" were some rural priests. Thus, the fate of the most famous methodological work of Pavlenkov wasn't easy. She was again requested to the special department of the academic committee of the ministry, created in 1869 in connection with the penetration of anti-government views into the pedagogical literature and performed the function of censorship. A member of this department, Kochetov, noted in his review that putting together, "allegedly according to methodological requirements", illustrations of a church lectern and stall, a rooster and a monk, a crown, a cow and a kokoshnik means desecration of sacred objects, compromised ministers of worship and monarchy, and aroused disrespect among students". Authorities were particularly enraged by placement of drawings of a gallows, a chain, an officer and a tsar, "necessary for studying the letter C," one after another. Vyatka artist V. I. Porfiriev illustrated the book [23, p. 32].

Vyatka governor Valery Ivanovich Charykov, who wished to familiarize himself with the book, found drawings in it depicting the emperor in porphyry and a crown, and in front of his soldier running away from the battlefield and saying at the same time: "How nice to die for the tsar and the fatherland." "I quite agree with you," says another soldier, overtaking the first one [24, p. 52].

It's not surprising that, in the end, the governor came to the quite natural conclusion that the book should be removed from libraries, since, among other things, it instilled Darwin's views on the origin of man and was "more harmful than the writings of Lasalle" [25, p. 200]. A special department of the scientific committee of the ministry of public education saw in the book veiled propaganda of Darwinism, which was especially persecuted in those years: "The comparison on page 25 of skeletons of a man and a monkey is inconvenient in the sense that it can give an excuse to an ill-intentioned teacher to develop a theory for children, the spread of which in public schools can't be allowed" [26, p. 24].

But most of all, censorship was confused by the very idea of mobile schools. Therefore, in an effort to prevent the spread of this type of educational institutions, under the cover of which populist revolutionaries could carry out anti-government activities, the censorship committee recommended the closure of mobile schools and decided to ban the "Visual Alphabet" as a manual that could be used in this type of schools, as the author himself publicly stated. The edition of the manual published in 1874 was destroyed. The very title of the book, which has become widely, but, alas, notorious, was banned. However, he continued to fight for his book. According to his confession, the "life or death" of the "Visual Alphabet" was for him almost the same as half of his own life and death. Truly, it was an alphabet born in captivity, as the modern biographer of Pavlenkov, Yuniy Alekseevich Gorbunov (1938-2021), rightly defined the situation with the book [27].

Pavlenkov was forced to use a trick. After making minor changes in the arrangement of drawings and replacing the previous title with another one ("Reading and writing from pictures"), he sent a copy of the corrected original to the censorship committees of Kazan, Moscow, Kiev and Riga, received the appropriate permission for publication in them, and without any difficulty in early 1876 he released 30 thousand copies of the new edition of actually the same "Visual Alphabet", but under a different title and without the designation of the author's surname [28, p. 8]. In the preface, in order to mislead censorship, Pavlenkov even ... "criticizes" the previously published Pavlenkov edition. As a result, the book became widely known before the author's cunning was discovered. Subsequently, upon Pavlenkov's return from exile to St. Petersburg, he managed to restore the former title, "Visual Alphabet".

The St. Petersburg edition of the Pavlenkov alphabet came out with the name of Blinov on the cover, who was forced to give his consent to this in the interests of the enlightenment, although he foresaw possible troubles for himself, which, indeed, didn't slow to affect: a search followed, suspension from teaching work. 15 years later, when references and censorious quibbles regarding this publication were far in the past, and it was possible to "safely" point to their authorship, in the preface to the next edition of the Explanation to the Visual Alphabet, he suddenly found it necessary to state the following: "The compilation of the "Visual Alphabet" until recent years was attributed to the the priest Blinov, who for a long time had nothing against it. But after reproaches that he addressed to me about the allegedly unfavorable consequences of such a misunderstanding, I consider it quite permissible for myself to declare now that father Blinov not only doesn't own a single line in the "Visual Alphabet" and "Reading-Writing from Pictures", but he didn't even believe in the possibility of the practical realization of the idea that I had put into the foundation of these ABC books" [21, p. 4].

Pavlenkov began to develop another new material to provide visual education in elementary school. He prepared for publication a book of "children's problems in pictures", which he called "Visual Inconsistencies". In this work, Pavlenkov for the first time took as a basis, so to speak, a negative element. The book should have included up to 450 drawings depicting various objects, actions and phenomena in obvious and visual inconsistency with reality regarding the number, size, shape, place, properties of objects, etc. According to the author, the inconsistencies should have served as a kind of incentive for the child to ask the questions "why?" and "why?". Unfortunately for the author, it didn't receive the expected application and success. Potential users of the manual were undoubtedly confused by Pavlenkov's very unsuccessful didactic approach. After all, as a rule, positive examples are given in textbooks, which are remembered by children. There was also a well-founded danger that incorrect examples would be remembered as correct [28, p. 9-10].

CONCLUSION

An analysis of Pavlenkov's educational activities gives grounds for an assertion that he contributed to the spread of education in the Vyatka region. He considered opening of schools and libraries to be the most important means of establishing literacy, and therefore he bequeathed his entire inheritance, consisting of 50000 books worth 800000 rubles, to open two thousand public rural libraries throughout Russia. In the Vyatka province by 1911, 194 Pavlenkov libraries were opened in eleven counties. After returning to St. Petersburg from Vyatka in December 1877, he directed his methodological and publishing activities, first of all, to provide public schools with high-quality textbooks. Compiled and repeatedly republished by him "Visual alphabet", "Visual-sound recipes", "Book for reading at school and at home", "300 written works", "Tasks for writing exercises in elementary school", "Initial spelling", "Manual for Sunday schools", books published by him of Ushinsky, Bunakov, Korf, Paulson and other authors earned Pavlenkov deep respect from the pedagogical community. At the same time, he invariably sought to give the best design to the published literature, which had an important educational value, encouraged children to take care of it [29, p. 76]. By the time of his return from Vyatka exile, he had issued, in general, only 16 single-volume editions with nominal value of about 18000 rubles. But on the day of his death, the number of publications was brought to 755 with a total circulation of over 3.5 million copies. The cost of the published ones was determined by the amount of 804628 rubles [28, p. 10].

Pavlenkov died on January 20 (February 1), 1900 in Nice, buried in St. Petersburg, on the Literary bridges of the Volkov Cemetery. He bequeathed his capital to set up free libraries and reading rooms in villages. In 1901-1911 two thousand free reading libraries were opened in 53 provinces. Most of all (more than two hundred) "Pavlenkov libraries" were opened in the Vyatka province.

According to the data of Vyatka librarian Elena Kozhinova, only in Yaransk District in 1907 there were 15 national libraries. Most of them found shelter under roofs of public schools, housed in a teacher's room or classroom, and sometimes just in a closet under a padlock in a school corridor. At the appointed time, they were opened and students, peasants and other representatives of village people chose to read a book. Pavlenkov's executor V. Ya. Yakovenko, who took care of the arrangement of libraries, monitored their condition, corresponded with county zemstvos, sent catalogs and books, studied demands of readers for literature.

Under Yakovenko, Pavlenkov's libraries were replenished with works of progressive writers. In the Soviet period, Pavlenkov libraries ceased to be funded and replenished with literature, and therefore soon ceased to exist; they were partially transformed into reading huts. Now there are four rural libraries on the territory of the Yaransk district of the Kirov region, opened at the beginning of the XX century at the expense of the educator, – in the villages of Kugusherga, Nikulyata, Shkalany and Nikolsk. Employees of the Yaransk centralized library system conduct search work related to Pavlenkov's personality: they collect photographic materials, copies of documents, establish contacts with local historians. Libraries are decorated with "Pavlenkov corners" and stands.

In the mid-1990s, a movement began to return the name of Pavlenkov to those libraries that were once opened from the fund named after him. By the decision of the Yaransk District Duma of the Kirov region of September 22, 1999, the Kugushersk village library was named after Pavlenkov. In 1997, an All-Russian public organization was formed under the name "Commonwealth of Pavlenkov Libraries". Its founder and first president was Yuniy Alekseevich Gorbunov, the author of a book about Pavlenkov [30]. Currently, it includes 317 rural libraries. In memory of the educator Pavlenkov, the Kirov regional scientific library named after Herzen regularly hosts scientific and practical conferences, – "Pavlenkov Readings", which gather book lovers from different regions of Russia.

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